

A Non-Intimidating Approach to Workflow Reproducibility in Bioinformatics

Adding Metadata to Research Objects through the Design and
Evaluation of Use-Focused Extensions to CWLProv

MSc Thesis Defense

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There exists a computational reproducibility crisis!

- **Computational reproducibility**: consistent results given the same input data and software
- In practice: Code and data are not shared or produce different output
- **Provenance**: the path from raw data to published results

Informal Data Citation for Data Sharing and Reuse Is More Common Than Formal Data Citation in Biomedical Fields

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An empirical analysis of journal policy effectiveness for computational reproducibility

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Workflow-centric research objects: A vision for the future

CWLProv: A model for sharing the results of a workflow execution

- CWL workflow description
- Input and (intermediate) output data
- Structured metadata (RDF) describing aggregated resources and their relations

Our research goal

Which metadata should be contained in (CWLProv) ROs?

RQ1: Which elements of a Bioinformatics workflow execution should be described in RO metadata, considering representative use cases of their provenance?

RQ2: How does provenance contained in ROs following the CWLProv community standard compare to the elements defined in answer to RQ1?

RQ3: How to improve CWLProv provenance such that it meets the requirements defined in the answer to RQ1?

Approach

Define relevant metadata for an example Bioinformatics workflow

Analyze CWLProv ROs for the presence of this metadata

Design solutions to improve CWLProv provenance

Implementing a workflow for epitope prediction in CWL

Focus on reproducibility

Use cases for associated ROs:

- U1: Workflow development
- U2: Workflow publishing
- U3: Understanding workflow
- U4: Reproducing workflow
- U5: Using model as a web service

From use cases to a taxonomy of provenance

Analysis of CWLProv - Results

Type	Subtype	Name	RDF	packed.cwl	primary-job.json	unstructured
T1	SC1	Workflow-level		(■)		
	SC2	Data-level			(□)	
	SC3	Execution-level *				
T2	D1	Data identification			(□)	
	D2	File characteristics	□		(□)	□
	D3	Data access			(□)	
	D4	Data mapping	■		□	□
T3	SW1	Software identification		(□)		
	SW2	Software documentation		(□)		
	SW3	Software access		(□)		
T4	WF1	Workflow software metadata	□	(■)		
	WF2	Workflow parameters	□	(■)		
	WF3	Workflow requirements		(■)		
T5	ENV1	Software environment *				
	ENV2	Hardware environment *				
	ENV3	Container image	□	□		□
T6	EX1	Timestamps	■			
	EX2	Consumed resources				□
	EX3	Workflow engine	□			
	EX4	Human agent	■			■

PROBLEM 1:
Computational environment missing

PROBLEM 2:
RDF description incomplete

SOLUTION:
Extend RDF graph

PROBLEM 3:
Strong dependence on manual annotations

SOLUTION:
Annotation scheme for input data

Vocabulary: based on Schema.org...

Schema.org	T2 element	Expected type
identifier	PID	URL
version	version	Number, Text
name	name	Text
description	description	Text
citation	citation	CreativeWork
includedInDataCatalog	database	DataCatalog
dateCreated	download date	Date, DateTime
distribution	URL to data	DataDownload
license	license	URL

Schema.org	Expected type	Explanation
query	Text	Query used (only for SearchAction)
object	Thing	Database or initial dataset
result	Thing	Resulting dataset
instrument	Thing	Tool used, e.g. for filtering
endTime	DateTime, Time	Time of action
agent	Organization, Person	Who performed the action
description	Text	Description of the action

... but extendable with other (domain-specific) ontologies

Example 1: annotating a FAIR dataset

- CWL-specific
- Minimum
- Optional
- Domain-specific

s: <http://schema.org/>
doi: <https://doi.org/>
edam: <http://edamontology.org/>

```
1 FAIR_file:
2 class: File
3 location: file://path/to/file.pdb
4 format: edam:format_1476 # pdb
5 s:identifier: doi:10.2210/pdb6nzn/pdb
6 s:version: "1.4"
7 s:description: "Amyloid fibril structure of
8 ↪ glucagon in pdb format."
9 s:name: "6NZN"
10 s:citation: # Primary publication
11   s:identifier: doi:10.1038/s41594-019-0238-6
12 s:includedInDataCatalog: # PDB
13   s:identifier: doi:10.25504/FAIRsharing.2t35ja
14 s:distribution: # Downloadable form of dataset
15 ↪ https://ftp.wwpdb.org/pub/pdb/data/structures
16 ↪ /divided/pdb/nz/pdb6nzn.ent.gz
17 s:additionalType:
18 - s:Dataset
19 - edam:data_1460 # protein structure
20 edam:has_topic: edam:topic_2814 # protein
21 ↪ structure analysis
```

Example 2: Representing the history of processed data

s: <http://schema.org/>
biotools: <https://bio.tools/>
doi: <https://doi.org/>
edam: <http://edamontology.org/>

```
1  cwlprov:prov:
2    pdb_search:
3      s:additionalType: s:SearchAction
4      s:query: "All proteins with at least 2 chains
5              ↪ deposited between 2010 and 2022"
6      s:object:
7        s:identifier: biotools:pdb
8        s:result: pdb_search_result
9        s:endTime: 2022-08-01
10     filtering_action:
11       s:additionalType: s:Action
12       s:object: pdb_search_result
13       s:instrument:
14         s:identifier: biotools:pisces
15       s:result: filtered_pdb_dataset
16
17     filtered_pdb_dataset:
18       class: Directory
19       location: file://path/to/directory/
```

Example 3: Annotating a collection of input parameters

```
1  input1: "string value"  
2  input2: 4  
3  input3:  
4    class: File  
5    location: file://path/to/file.txt  
6  
7  s:description: "Workflow run without input feature  
  ↪ X to test effect on model performance."
```

s: <http://schema.org/>

Conclusion

Defined a taxonomy of relevant metadata based on one Bioinformatics workflow

Analyzed CWLProv for the representation of this metadata

Designed an extension to the RDF provenance graph to represent richer annotations

Proposed guidelines for structured annotation of input data

Future work

Realize CWLProv extension in CWL engines

Define structured representation of software and computational environment

Apply provenance taxonomy to RO-Crate specification

Build tools for extraction of metadata from ROs

Design mechanisms for automated collection of metadata

Supplementary
material

Provenance graph in CWLProv community standard

Propagation of workflow annotations to RDF provenance graph

Propagation of actions to RDF provenance graph

